

COMPLEX FORMATION IN AQUEOUS MERCURIC CHLORIDE AND POTASSIUM IODIDE BY CONDUCTIVITY, VISCOSITY AND REFRACTIVITY MEASUREMENTS.

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Complex formation in aqueous mercuric chloride and potassium iodide has been studied by the conductivity, viscosity, and refractivity measurements. The occurrence of breaks (maxima or minima) in specific conductivity, viscosity, and refractivity composition curves has been attributed to the existence of molecular complexes of mercuric chloride and potassium iodide.

Jaques ("Complex Ions in Aqueous Solutions," Longmans, Green & Co., London, 1914, p. 48; has given an exhaustive review of the earlier work on mercuric chloride-alkali chloride complexes in aqueous system. The complexes of the type M_2HgX_4 , $MHgX_3$, in aqueous and non-aqueous solutions seem to have been reported by many investigators on freezing point, E.M.F., solubility and other independent grounds.* The importance of the reaction between KI and $HgCl_2$ in analytical chemistry was pointed out by Koninck and Lebrun (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1902, II, 72), Kolthoff (*Pharm. Weekblad*, 1920, 57, 836) and others. Complexes of $HgCl_2$ or HgI_2 with KI in alcohol or acetone solutions have been studied by conductivity measurements (cf. Pernot, *Compt. rend.*, 1927, 185, 950; *Ann. Chim.*, 1931, x, 15, 5; Gallais, *Compt. rend.*, 1932, 195, 875). Foote and Martin (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1909, 41, 451) measured the conductivities of alkali chlorides in fused $HgCl_2$ at 282° ; abnormal rise in conductivity was attributed to complex formation. Job (*Compt. rend.*, 1925, 180, 1932), Shibata and Ionone (*Japan J. Chem.*, 1926, 2, 109), and Samuel, Zaman and Zubairy (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1935, 9, 491) studied the formation of complex mercury salts by spectroscopic means. The present work, being an outcome of interesting results of Sharma and Kadhe in these laboratories, is intended to study complex formation in aqueous $HgCl_2$ and KI by conductivity, viscosity and refractivity measurements.

* Cf. LeBlanc and Noyes, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1890, 6, 401; Clayton, *Chem. News*, 1894, 70, 102; Pawloff, *J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, 32, 732, Dobroserdoff, *ibid.*, 1901, 33, 392; Sherill, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1903, 43, 705; Sand and Breest, *ibid.*, 1907, 59, 424; Dawson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 85, 870; Bourion and Rouyer, *Compt. rend.*, 1924, 178, 86, 1171; Vajnik and Uberoy, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 802.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Merck's guaranteed extra pure mercuric chloride and potassium iodide were used. Conductivity measurements of aqueous KI ($M/20$ and $M/50$) in presence of varying proportions of $HgCl_2$ were made at 15° and 30° , observing the usual precautions (*cf.* earlier communications by Joshi and Solanki, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 323; 1940, **17**, 627). The maximum concentration of $HgCl_2$ was such as to avoid the actual precipitation of HgI_2 in the solution. The cell constant determined by using freshly prepared $N/50$ -KCl solution at $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ was 0.3776. The same cell constant was used for calculating the conductivity at 15° and 30° , its variation with temperature, especially for 5° - 10° differences, being negligible.

The viscosity determinations of the mixed solutions of KI and $HgCl_2$ were also made at 15° and 30° by adopting Ostwald's method. Extreme precautions were taken specially in cleaning the viscometer and in maintaining the temperature control within 0.05° . The densities corresponding to these solutions were determined at the above temperatures.

The refractive index for the sodium line was determined for each of the above mixtures by means of Pulfrich refractometer at 15° and 30° with the usual precautions.

The strength of the mixture in terms of its components, potassium iodide and mercuric chloride, is recorded in column 1 in Tables I—IV; the concentrations of the components are expressed for the system *after mixing*. Column 2 gives the resistance in ohms for the mixed solutions. In column 3 are given the specific conductivities in μ hos for the mixtures; in column 4 are given the specific conductivities for the corresponding concentrations of mercuric chloride present in the mixture as shown in column 1. Column 5 gives the percentage departure of the specific conductivity of the mixture (column 3) from that calculated by applying the additive rule. Columns 6 and 7 give respectively the viscosities and densities of the mixtures. The refractivity data for these mixtures are shown in column 8 and 9; column 8 gives the angle of emergence after correction for zero error and column 9 gives the refractive index for sodium line. All these results for the mixtures are shown graphically in Figs. 1 to 4. The quantities, *viz.*, the specific conductivity, percentage departure of the specific conductivity from that obtained by the additive rule, viscosity, density and refractive index are plotted against the concentration of mercuric chloride present in the system by appropriate selection of scale units in the same figure to economise space (Figs. 1 to 4).

TABLE I.

Temperature = $30 \pm 0.05^\circ$. Mixture of M/20-KI and HgCl₂. Sp. conductivity of water = 1.37×10^{-6} mhos.

Comp. of mixture after mixing.	R of mixture in ohms.	Sp. condy. of mixture in mhos.	% Departure of the sp. condy. of mixture from additive rule	Viscosity of mixture in absolute units.	Density of the mixture in g/c.c.	Angle of emergence corrected for zero error.	Refractive index of mixture.
M/20 KI only	51.35	0.0073516		0.0081594	1.0097	67° 13'	1.3330704
M/20 KI+M/400 HgCl ₂	52.80	0.0071506	3.12	0.0080996	1.0104	67° 10'	1.3333044
M/20 KI+2M/400 "	53.65	0.0070356	4.75	0.0081190	1.0110	67° 12'	1.331484
M/20 KI+3M/400 "	54.35	0.0069456	6.06	0.0080790	1.0115	67° 10'	1.3333044
M/20 KI+4M/400 "	54.90	0.0068756	7.08	0.0080977	1.0122	67° 9'	1.3333824
M/20 KI+7M/600 "	55.40	0.0068146	7.98	0.0080981	1.0125	67° 9'	1.3333824

TABLE II.

Temperature = $15 \pm 0.05^\circ$. Mixture of M/20-KI and HgCl₂. Sp. conductivity of water = 1.09×10^{-6} mhos.

Comp. of mixture after mixing.	R of mixture in ohms.	Sp. condy. of mixture in mhos.	% Departure of the sp. condy. of mixture from additive rule.	Viscosity of mixture in absolute units.	Density of mixture in g c.c	Angle of emergence corrected for zero error.	Refractive index of the mixture.
M/20 KI only	69.5	0.005432		0.011588	1.00332	66° 55'	1.3344278
M/20 KI+M/400 HgCl ₂	70.4	0.005362	1.56	0.011532	1.00357	66° 53'	1.3346858
M/20 KI+2M/400 "	71.3	0.005291	2.88	0.011565	1.00384	66° 53'	1.3345858
M/20 KI+3M/400 "	73.1	0.005164	5.31	0.011642	1.00424	66° 52'	1.3346648
M/20 KI+4M/400 "	74.45	0.005070	7.10	0.011610	1.00469	66° 51'	1.3347438
M/20 KI+7M/600 "	75.35	0.005009	8.27			66° 51'	1.3347438

TABLE III.

Temperature = $30 \pm 0.05^\circ$. Mixture of $M/50$ -KI and $HgCl_2$. Sp. conductivity of water = 1.37×10^{-6} mhos.

Comp. of mixture after mixing.	R of mixture in ohms.	Sp. condy. of mixture in mhos.	Sp. condy. of $HgCl_2$ in mhos.	% Departure of sp. condy. of mixture from additive rule.	Viscosity of mixture in absolute units.	Density of mixture in g./c.c.	Angle of emergence corrected for zero error.	Refractive index of the mixture.
$M/50$ KI only	126.5	0.002984			0.0080429	1.00361	$67^\circ 22'$	1.3323704
$M/50$ KI + $M/1000$ $HgCl_2$	128.2	0.002944	0.00002353	2.08	0.0080263	1.00402	$67^\circ 20'$	1.3325244
$M/50$ KI + $2M/1000$ "	129.5	0.002915	0.00002802	3.22	0.0080357	1.00437	$67^\circ 21'$	1.3324474
$M/50$ KI + $3M/1000$ "	130.0	0.002904	0.00003175	3.71	0.0080024	1.00461	$67^\circ 20'$	1.3325844
$M/50$ KI + $4M/1000$ "	131.6	0.002868	0.00003686	5.06	0.0080166	1.00485	$69^\circ 19'$	1.3326024
$M/50$ KI + $5M/1000$ "	134.3	0.002810	0.00003997	7.05	0.0080178	1.00507	$67^\circ 19'$	1.3326024

TABLE IV.

Temperature = $15 \pm 0.05^\circ$. Mixture of $M/50$ -KI and $HgCl_2$. Sp. conductivity of water = 1.09×10^{-6} mhos.

Comp. of mixture after mixing.	R of mixture in ohms.	Sp. condy. of mixture in mhos.	Sp. condy. of $HgCl_2$ in mhos.	% Departure of sp. condy. of mixture from additive rule.	Viscosity of mixture in absolute units.	Density of mixture in g./c.c.	Angle of emergence corrected for zero error.	Refractive index of the mixture.
$M/50$ KI only	168.7	0.002238			0.011611	1.00164	$67^\circ 4'$	1.3337208
$M/50$ KI + $M/1000$ $HgCl_2$	171.4	0.002202	0.00001104	2.09	0.011618	1.00178	$67^\circ 3'$	1.3338768
$M/50$ KI + $2M/1000$ "	174.7	0.002161	0.00001402	4.04	0.011620	1.00190	$67^\circ 2'$	1.3318768
$M/50$ KI + $3M/1000$ "	175.5	0.002151	0.00001617	4.58	0.011643	1.00213	$67^\circ 1'$	1.3339548
$M/50$ KI + $4M/1000$ "	177.7	0.002123	0.00001859	5.92	0.011626	1.00234	$67^\circ 0'$	1.3340328
$M/50$ KI + $5M/1000$ "	180.2	0.002094	0.00002027	7.27	0.011626		$67^\circ 0'$	1.3340328

Cell constant in all cases was 0.3776.

FIG. 1.
Temp. = 30°.

D I S C U S S I O N .

Data shown under column 4 in Tables I-IV indicate that HgCl₂ behaves as an extremely weak electrolyte, almost a non-electrolyte as is obvious from the exceedingly low order of the specific conductivities in agreement with the results previously published (*cf.* Joshi and Solanki, *loc. cit.*). Results in column 3 show that with the addition of HgCl₂, the specific conductivity of the resulting mixture of KI(*M*/*20* and *M*/*50*) and HgCl₂ gets diminished considerably, the diminution produced increased with increased concentration of HgCl₂. In other words, the specific conductivities of the resulting mixtures show considerable departures (results in column 5) from those calculated by applying the additive law for the corresponding mixtures, *viz.*, the specific conductivity of the mixture equals the sum of the specific conductivities of the two components, each determined separately. For mixtures of certain salts, such as NaCl and KCl, for which no complex formation is anticipated, the deviations from additive behaviour are less than the experimental error in conductivity (*cf.* Sandonini, *Gazetta*, 1916, *ii*, 46, 205; also Jones and Oata, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1899, 22, 5) and

refractivity measurements (*cf.* Eberhard, Rimbach and Wintgen, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1910, 74, 230). Results for the conductivity of aqueous benzoic

FIG. 2.
Temp. = 15°.

acid (*cf.* earlier communication from these laboratories, Joshi and Solanki, *loc. cit.*) in the presence of LiCl, NaCl, KCl, RbCl, etc., show that additive law holds for the mixture. The observed diminution in conductivity and correspondingly the departure of KI and HgCl₂ might, therefore, be attributed to complex formation. The molecular complexes of HgCl₂ and KI have been shown to exist, independently by several observers: Gallais (*loc. cit.*) by conductivity measurements, Shibata and Ionone (*loc. cit.*) and Job (*loc. cit.*) by spectroscopic methods, Bourion and Rouyer (*loc. cit.*) ebullioscopically, Yajnik and Uberoy (*loc. cit.*) by viscosity measurements and also by refractivity measurements. The specific conductivity and its percentage departure graphs in Figs. 1-4 and also viscosity and refractive index graphs in Figs. 1-3 show remarkable similarity, *i.e.*, while the viscosity increases, refractive index decreases roughly to the same extent until in the former case a maximum and in the latter case a minimum are obtained. The occurrence of this discontinuity (except in the case of density), *i.e.*, the minima in specific conductivity-, and in refractivity-, and

maxima in viscosity-composition curves can, therefore, be taken as indicative of complex formation and the composition of the complex formed being

FIG. 3.
Temp. = 30°

FIG. 4.
Temp. = 15°

noted from the composition corresponding to the position of minima or maxima in the respective curves (*cf.* Figs. 1-4). All the measurements lead probably to the existence of a complex of KI and HgCl_2 in the molecular proportion, 10 KI, HgCl_2 . Viscosity measurements indicated the existence of another complex 20 KI, 3HgCl_2 . Our data also show an indication of another break in the respective curves corresponding to a point in the vicinity of maximum concentration of HgCl_2 tried, roughly corresponding to a formula, 4-5 KI, HgCl_2 . The breaks in the respective curves are sharp and well defined, especially in concentrated solutions and at a low temperature thus showing that the complexes formed in the aqueous system dissociate at high temperature and dilution.

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